

www.ijasre.net
ISSN : 2454-8006

Certificate of Publication

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
ADVANCES IN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND ENGINEERING
(IJASRE)** Crossref DOI: 10.31695/IJASRE

This is to certify that
Uwaibi E. Noel et. al.,

Affiliation: Edo University Iyamho, Nigeria

Has Published a paper entitled

Facility Readiness for Childhood Routine Immunization Services in Primary Healthcare Centres
in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria

In International Journal of Advances in Scientific Research and Engineering

DOI:10.31695/IJASRE.2020.33779

Volume 6, Issue 4 Month April -2020

Head Of Publishing